
Citation for the Presentation of the 2024 ICPE Medal
to
Dr David R. Sokoloff

Professor David R. Sokoloff is awarded the ICPE Medal for 2024 in recognition of his sustained international efforts in physics education during nearly four decades. Dr. Sokoloff has devoted his career to developing new active learning strategies and tools for teaching physics, researching their effectiveness, and disseminating them around the world, including to high school teachers and university faculty in developing nations. His work has resulted in widely used, published teaching materials, hundreds of pedagogy workshops in the U.S. and around the world, hundreds of presentations at national and international conferences, and numerous articles and chapters in peer-reviewed books and proceedings. Furthermore, he has advanced the nurturing of physics education research by serving in leadership positions, elected to the four-year leadership cycle of the American Association of Physics Teachers (AAPT) in 2008 (serving as President in 2011) and also serving for seven years as a member of IUPAP Commission 14 (2018-2024).

In recognition of these contributions to physics education, Prof. Sokoloff was awarded the 2007 Robert A. Millikan and the 2010 Hans Christian Oersted medals of the AAPT. He was awarded the 2010 Excellence in Physics Education Award by the American Physical Society (APS) (with Priscilla Laws and Ronald Thornton, his long-time collaborators). In 2011, he and the Active Learning in Optics and Photonics (ALOP) workshop team were awarded the SPIE Educator Award. He has been awarded two Fulbright Senior Specialist Grants, in Argentina (2011) and in Japan (2018). He was also awarded the Latin American Physics Education Network (LAPEN) Medal in 2011 and the GIREP Medal in 2020.

He was Professor of Physics at the University of Oregon in Eugene, Oregon, USA from 1978-2003, and is currently Professor of Physics, Emeritus. Prior to his current position, he was a faculty member at Western Illinois University and University of Michigan, Dearborn. He has

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held visiting positions at California Polytechnic State University, Tufts University, Swinburne University of Technology, and Universidad Nacional de San Luis, San Luis, Argentina, and also spent a year as Science Director of WISTEC, the hands-on science center in Eugene, Oregon.

Since 2005, he has been a member of the UNESCO team presenting Active Learning in Optics and Photonics (ALOP) workshops, mostly in developing countries. Thirty seven ALOPs have been presented around the world including Ghana, Tunisia (2), Morocco, India (2), Tanzania, Brazil, Mexico, Zambia, Cameroon, Colombia, Nepal (2), Chile, The Philippines, Rwanda, Armenia, Thailand, Ethiopia, Indonesia (3), Mauritius, Panama, Bolivia, Ukraine, Ecuador, Thailand, and Peru. He is the editor of the *Active Learning in Optics and Photonics Training Manual*, published by UNESCO for use in these workshops. He has presented other active learning in physics workshops in Chile, Colombia, Peru, Ecuador, Mexico, Australia, New Zealand, Malaysia, The Philippines, Argentina, Canada, France, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Slovenia, Slovakia, Czech Republic, Vietnam, Korea, China, Sri Lanka, Turkey, and throughout the U.S.

In light of his outstanding achievements, Prof. David Sokoloff exemplifies the ideals of excellence, dedication, and leadership in physics education the ICPE Medal was created to honor. With admiration and respect, we bestow upon Professor David R. Sokoloff the ICPE Medal in recognition of his profound impact and unwavering commitment to advancing the frontiers of physics education. The award ceremony will take place at the International Conference on Physics Education, 2025 in Ropar, India.

